

THE RELEVANCE OF USING INTERESTING GAMES ON GEOGRAPHY LESSONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7990745>

Abstract. *This article will talk about how relevant the use of interesting games during the lesson is when organizing geography lessons, that is, in a good explanation of the subject information to students. A number of techniques that can be used effectively in geography lessons are also cited throughout the article.*

Keywords: *tolerance, geography, concept, method, pedagogical skill, atlas.*

Introduction. Each subject passed in the school system is considered important for the future scientific and life activities of students. There is also a much more important role in our life in the science of geography, which is associated with the environment in which the individual lives. Thanks to this, teaching this subject requires much more skill and methodological knowledge from the teacher. While each subject in the school system serves for the perspective of an individual, we can safely call it humanization.

Humanization of education, the formation of the educator as a person in the center of all pedagogical views, the radical change in the relationship of the student and teacher, educator-educator, the independence and initiative of society on the basis of human life and health, their rights, experiences of the national and world educational system on the basis of individual development, universal values, free choice of, it is necessary to have qualifications and skills.

The history of the development of society proves that the higher the level of taste of members of society, the higher the socio-economic development and the development of human spiritual and cultural development, its multilingualism, multiethality, tolerance, that is, tolerance. To do this, it is necessary to change the worldview of our young people, raise their knowledge and spirituality to the level of World templates.[1]

Main part. The widespread adoption of modern pedagogical technologies in the process of reading increases the learning of teaching. In order to achieve knowledge in knowledge, it is necessary, first of all, to use the latest achievements and discoveries of Science and technology in the teaching process, to create academic disciplines on the basis of science, to introduce students to scientific research methods. It forms the skill of students to approach various science and technology innovations in an objective way. As the student assimilates scientific knowledge, his ability to think grows and develops. The widespread use of modern pedagogical technologies in the process of reading again forms creativity in students. By creativity we understand that it is not the creation of some object or work of art that can approach each task from its point of view, think independently on one problem, attribute all the knowledge gained in the process of reading to the phenomena that are going on in life and analyze the uoar. In the process of studying again, independence is brought up in students.

The following activities are carried out in higher educational institutions to increase the productivity of research work, to attract young people to scientific activities, to form an innovative infrastructure of science:

- introduction of mechanisms to support the activities of publishing articles in prestigious international scientific journals;

- development of fundamental, practical and innovative scientific research, preservation of existing scientific schools and creation of new ones, strengthening their human resources, promoting the wide involvement of talented young people in science.[2]

Including, as we noted above, the use of pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, interesting games is important in the effective organization of the geography lesson in schools. No matter how old it is, if a lesson is taken continuously only through the provision of scientific information, students will quickly get tired and have difficulty mastering the topic. Since geography is a science that maintains a connection directly with the world around us, with the environment in which we live, it is necessary for students to master this science in an excellent way so that the pedagogue can exercise all the skills he has.

Below we will cite a number of methods and games for an interesting organization of classes. As you know, any method and game directly in the lesson serves to ensure the activity of the reader and fully explain the subject information. For example, in the game "Wonderland", students are initially drawn into 3 groups. Each group is asked a question on the topic mentioned separately. From each group, 3 students who answered the question first are selected and a heated competition is thrown between them. The teacher writes on a piece of paper one of the terms he taught the children in the lessons passed to the board, concealing each letter of it using papers. After 3 students go to the board, the teacher opens 1 cell of the term. If one can find the entire letters of the term through the same 1 letter, the same reader will be the winner. If they cannot find the adjective after specifying 1 letter, the next letter will open. After the term is found, it is commented on by the reader.

Another game that sufficiently increases student activity in the classroom is the "right-wrong" game. In this game, students are told something about geography. The main thing about this is that not all data will be correct. Readers are also told misinformation in conjunction with the correct information. In the process, the reader must focus all his attention on the information being given and, alternatively, analyze and determine whether the info is correct or not. For example, a teacher may say "the Uzbek republic borders on 6 states". Naturally, a student who has mastered geography immediately determines that this information is a mistake. Or if not, it is possible to further strengthen their knowledge and, the main thing, interest all students in the lesson by presenting such erroneous reflections as "there are 7 continents on Earth", "the highest peak is Pamir", "the air temperature cools in every certain meter under the Earth".

The game "memory exercise" attracts students to the lesson, where it also performs the tasks of testing their memory and strengthening their memory. This game is played as follows: the teacher can play this game in 6, 10 or the whole class, depending on his discretion. Students are sequentially placed and utter a term referring to geography. The 1st reader says, then the 2nd reader says the term the 1st reader says and one more, while the 3rd reader says the terms the 1st and 2nd readers say and one more term, while the 4th reader says the terms the 1st, 2nd and 3rd readers say, and so on, continuing in this way. Through this game, students' memory is strengthened and their interest in the lesson is further increased.

Conclusion. In place of the conclusion, it is worth saying that the role of qiaqarli games in the effective organization of the geography lesson is benihoya senior. Since it is the main task of

the teacher to interest each student in the lessons and deliver the subject information to the students, he must have a treasure trove of inexhaustible methods and knowledge.

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